

Recording setup information – AASIS data collection

1. University of Helsinki

Cameras:

- 2 Blackmagic Studio Camera 4K Pro cameras filming one speaker each.
- 1 Canon EOS M50 Mark II camera filming both speakers.
- 1 Insta360 ONE RS 1-inch 360 camera filming both speakers' faces directly. The camera is set up on a small tripod on the table between the speakers.
- Speaker A is 2.2m from camera 1. Speaker B is 1.7m from camera 2. They are both about 3m away from camera 3. They are about 70cm away from camera 4 if they are sitting straight.

Microphones:

- 2 single person Lavalier microphones (SP Tech Lavalier microphone ALM-XLR2), which are 15cm-30cm from the participants mouths.
- 1 whole-room AK Acoustics C 542 BL boundary microphone on the table in front of the participants. The participants are 1m from the whole-room microphone on the table.
- Backup audio: Zoom recorder connected to two overhead microphones, which are mounted on tripods.

Cameras and microphones are synced with Blackmagic ATEM SDI Extreme ISO mixer, which is controlled with the ATEM software control app.

Participants are sitting 1.5m from each other with a low table in between them. The researcher is sitting around 2m from the participants (see last picture, p. 3).

The recording setup is similar to the pictures below (the camera in the corner in the last picture (p. 3) is not used):

2. University of Jyväskylä

Cameras:

- 2 Blackmagic Ursa Broadcast G2 cameras filming one speaker each.
- Blackmagic Ursa Broadcast G2 camera filming both speakers.
- 1 Insta360 ONE X 360 camera filming both speakers' faces directly.

Microphones:

- 2 single person microphones (Work XS 1000 Pro).
- 1 whole-room Shure MX391 microphone on the table in front of the participants.

The recordings were supervised by a university technician.

3. Aalto University

Cameras:

- 2 Sony FDR-AX53B 4K cameras filming one speaker each.
- 1 Sony FDR-AX53B 4K camera filming both speakers.
- 1 Insta360 ONE X2 camera filming both speakers' faces directly. The camera is set up on a small tripod on the table between the speakers.

Microphones:

- 2 single person microphones (Shure SM7B).
- 1 whole-room Rode Wireless GO microphone on the table in front of the participants.
- Backup audio: The cameras' microphones.

The single microphone on the right records audio into the right channel, and the single microphone on the left record audio into the left channel.

The cameras and microphones are synced with Blackmagic ATEM Mini Pro ISO and Sound devices 302 field mixer. The ATEM mini is controlled with the ATEM software control app.

Participants are sitting around 1.1m away from each other with a low table in between them. Researcher is around 2m away from both participants, separated by an opaque partition so that the participants cannot see the researcher during spoken performance.

Unlike the University of Helsinki and the University of Jyväskylä, which use rooms specifically designed for video and audio recording, Aalto University converts a regular meeting room to a recording space. As a result, some ambient noise and noticeable echo are present in Aalto's recordings. The cameras may also capture shadows of people walking around the office. The individual personal microphones are sensitive and can pick up the opposite speaker's voice.

The room is also equipped with extra lighting (Ledgo LG-E268C Light LED-panel kit), which helps brighten the participants' faces (see picture below).

